

Analysis of the Effect of Self-Efficacy and Organization Climate on Employee Engagement with Organization Commitment as a Mediator (Case Study in PT. ADL)

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Abstract:- Self-Efficacy is a psychic symptom that often occurs throughout the world. Anxiety can result in lowering performance levels, other components such as Organization Climate (IO) and Organization Commitment (KO) are thought to be related to Employee Engagement (EE) which affects loyalty, morale and a high sense of belonging to the company. This study aims to test the influence between the variables of Self Efficacy, Organization Climate, Organization Commitment, and Employee Engagement on PT. ADL. The research method used is a quantitative descriptive method with primary data taken through a questionnaire of 100 respondents in PT. ADL. Hypothesis testing using the SmartPLS 3.0 program. The results of this study show that the influence of employee SE on EEE in general does not have a close relationship. Meanwhile, IO to EE, KO to EE, SE to KO, IO to KO in general all have a significant relationship.

Keywords:- Self-Efficacy (SE), Organization Climate (IO), Organization Commitment (KO), Employee Engagement (EE)

I. INTRODUCTION

Facing fierce and competitive competition, the company recruits only the best people and encourages its employees to do their best and be responsible as part of professional development and high commitment. On the other hand, employees are unique individuals, they have development needs, a desire to develop, and a sense of value. The loss of the company's best employees will have an impact on the company's business processes.

PT. ADL is a company engaged in the IT field. The company focuses on planning and developing mobile internet technologies supported by a team of experienced and experts in their fields. In the rapid development of technology today PT. ADL continues to develop its human resources, this is done so that the company can continue to compete in growing consumer confidence. In terms of improving the welfare of PT. ADL has made various efforts to increase employee engagement including by making the status of a permanent employee, a large salary, a good career path and bonuses at the end of each year. But in reality, problems still arise with employee engagement.

In the period from 2018 to 2022, PT. ADL shows a trend of labour turnover (LTO) that increases every year. The following is the data of LTO PT. ADL in the period from 2018 to 2022.

Year	Labour Turnover Intention			Percentage
	In	Out	Total	
2018	2	2	150	1.33%
2019	3	1	152	0.66%
2020	4	4	152	2.63%
2021	3	3	152	1.97%
2022	1	4	149	2.69%

Table 1: Labor Turnover Rate of PT. ADL

The data above shows that as of July 10, 2022, the LTO has reached 2.69%. This is if there is no proper management of HR management, it is possible that the upward trend will continue to grow.

Head Office of PT. ADL consists of 6 work units with a total of 150 employees, in each work unit competent human resources are needed and have a high level of discipline. Employee engagement that exists in employees can affect the level of employee discipline, such as in terms of employee attendance. The following is a report on the attendance of PT. ADL consisting of 6 work units.

Work units	A	B	C	D	E	F
January	58,3	48,8	87,5	35	71,8	63,3
February	73,3	47,5	90,8	58,3	67,4	71,7
March	76,4	49,2	80,6	67,9	67,2	71,8
April	86	49,2	80,6	81,3	64,6	58,7
May	74,7	46,1	83,6	65,6	70,3	51,5
June	86,2	44,7	89,6	92,1	87	82,2
July	73,3	44,2	77,5	62,6	63	80
August	61,7	47,7	86,7	63,1	65,2	50
September	81,3	55,2	79,1	59,4	55,8	49,8
October	92	54,9	95	85,9	80,6	94,2
November	79,2	50,2	84,3	59,4	55,8	91,5
December	78,5	48	78,8	53,8	55	76

Table 2: Presence of PT. ADL 2021

Based on the table above, the employee attendance rate is quite low on a monthly basis. From the table above, it can be seen that the percentage of employee attendance rates

tends to increase and decrease during 2021. The lowest percentage of attendance occurred in January, which was 35% in work unit D which means that the absenteeism rate in work unit D reached 65% and in other work units the attendance rate fluctuated. The level of employee absenteeism is an important factor in employee engagement.

Self-efficacy trusts the ability of the self to organize and perform the actions necessary to generate a certain level of achievement. However, the self-efficacy of PT ADL has decreased, marked by the company's targets that are often not achieved every month and the lack of cooperation between groups which causes the amount of overtime to increase every month. The amount of overtime payment for PT ADL employees can be seen from the graphic image as follows.

Fig. 1: Total Overtime Payment of PT ADL for the Period of January – June 2021

In addition, based on the results of initial interviews at PT. ADL obtained information that there were symptoms of problems related to employee engagement. Therefore, it is interesting for researchers to conduct research related to employee engagement problems in PT. ADL because employees will not leave their jobs if they feel attached to their work.

II. LITERATURE

A. Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy as an individual's assessment of their ability to organize and perform the actions necessary to achieve the type of planned activity [1]. From this understanding, it can be concluded that self-efficacy is a person's belief in his ability to complete a task in all circumstances by means of self-control and everything around him. Self-efficacy determines whether we engage in certain behaviors, how well we can resist difficulties or failures, and how successes or failures on certain tasks affect our future behavior. Positive self-efficacy is the belief that we are capable of performing the desired behavior [1].

B. Organization Climate

The organization climate as a relatively constant quality of the internal environment of the organization, experienced by the members of the organization, affects their behavior, and can be described as a set of characteristics or characteristics of the organization. In addition, it can also be described as the organization climate as a human

environment in which members of the organization perform their work. This definition can refer to the environment of a department, industry or organization as a whole. The organizational climate has 8 (eight) dimensions, namely autonomy, unity (cohesion), pressure, support, trust, recognition, fairness, and innovation [2].

C. Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is the most important function that drives consistent performance, achievement, and improvement throughout the year [3]. Employee engagement isn't just a buzzword – it has a clear relationship with the organization, which improves performance. Efficiency and productivity are critical to progress in a highly competitive market [4]. All organizations are strongly leaning forward to improving the form and quality of employee performance through good people management [5].

D. Organization commitment

Organization commitment is important as a condition for an employee who is aligned with the goals or achievements of the organization with a view to continuing the organization. There are three things in an individual's attitude to strength that can be identified from the influence of the individual on neighboring organizations. This setting can be identified as follows [6].

- Acceptance of the goals and values of the organization through beliefs
- Willingness to participate in the activities of the organization
- Great desire to strengthen the positive role of local organizations.

In addition, attachment to employees also has characteristics, namely, rarely graduating, rarely being late, feeling satisfied, unwilling to delegate work, and being highly motivated to work at a higher level than expected to achieve good performance and success [6].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Here's the frame of thought developed in the research.

Fig. 2: Conceptual Framework

Based on the picture above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

- H1: Self Efficacy has a positive and significant effect on Employee Engagement
- H2: Organization climate has a positive and significant effect on Employee Engagement
- H3: Employee Engagement has a positive and significant effect on organization commitment
- H4: Self Efficacy has a positive and significant effect on organization commitment
- H5: Organization Climate positively and significantly affects organization commitment
- H6: Organization Commitment Mediates Self Efficacy relationship with employee engagement
- H7: Organization commitment the relationship between the organization climate and employee engagement

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study, the authors used quantitative analysis methods. The author distributed a questionnaire of 100 respondents at PT. ADL to analyze. To analyze the data, the authors used the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with SmartPLS to validate measurements and structural models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The highest number of respondents was male as much as 66%. While the number of female respondents was 34% of the data of 100 respondents obtained, the composition of respondents based on gender was 66 respondents or as many as male and the remaining 34 people were female following the results of the data analysis that has been carried out.

Variable	Indicator	Employee Engagement	Organization Climate	Organization Commitment	Self Efficacy
Employee Engagement	EA1	0.78			
	EA2	0.758			
	EA3	0.781			
	EA4	0.741			
	EA5	0.739			
	EA6	0.748			
	ED1	0.725			
	ED2	0.72			
	ED3	0.755			
	ED4	0.77			
	ED5	0.748			
	ED6	0.744			
	ED7	0.723			
	EV1	0.774			
EV2	0.771				
EV3	0.745				
EV4	0.783				
Organization Climate	IO1		0.823		
	IO2		0.78		
	IO3		0.785		
	IO4		0.755		
	IO5		0.792		
	IO6		0.734		
	IO7		0.755		
	IO8		0.745		
	IO9		0.71		
	IO10		0.754		
Organization Commitment	KA1			0.742	
	KA2			0.756	
	KA3			0.751	
	KA4			0.761	
	KA5			0.755	
	KA6			0.78	
	KK1			0.754	
	KK2			0.757	
	KK3			0.756	
	KK4			0.739	
	KN1			0.797	
	KN2			0.74	
	KN3			0.737	
	KN4			0.796	
Self Efficacy	SE1				0.839
	SE2				0.858
	SE3				0.826
	SE4				0.807
	SE5				0.817

Table 3: Outer Loading

This shows that variable indicators that have a loading factor value greater than 0.70 have a high level of validity, thus meeting the convergent validity.

	Employee Engagement (Y)	Organization Climate(X2)	Organization Commitment(Z)	Self Efficacy (X1)
EA1	0.78	0.621	0.682	0.619
EA2	0.758	0.693	0.704	0.646
EA3	0.781	0.606	0.684	0.615
EA4	0.741	0.691	0.711	0.705
EA5	0.739	0.68	0.707	0.686
EA6	0.748	0.612	0.711	0.649
ED1	0.725	0.675	0.711	0.682
ED2	0.72	0.694	0.704	0.686
ED3	0.755	0.663	0.711	0.698
ED4	0.77	0.763	0.716	0.632
ED5	0.748	0.707	0.693	0.642
ED6	0.744	0.695	0.673	0.676
ED7	0.723	0.733	0.712	0.629
EV1	0.774	0.666	0.715	0.613
EV2	0.771	0.655	0.723	0.66
EV3	0.745	0.64	0.681	0.61
EV4	0.783	0.676	0.66	0.613
IO1	0.655	0.823	0.7	0.726
IO10	0.669	0.754	0.692	0.684
IO2	0.688	0.78	0.676	0.661
IO3	0.662	0.785	0.708	0.69
IO4	0.641	0.755	0.691	0.694
IO5	0.728	0.792	0.648	0.66
IO6	0.723	0.734	0.704	0.658
IO7	0.718	0.755	0.7	0.637
IO8	0.707	0.745	0.714	0.683
IO9	0.65	0.71	0.719	0.685
KA1	0.662	0.663	0.742	0.737
KA2	0.677	0.73	0.756	0.747
KA3	0.702	0.671	0.751	0.713
KA4	0.73	0.634	0.761	0.639
KA5	0.683	0.675	0.755	0.715
KA6	0.758	0.678	0.78	0.679
KK1	0.681	0.671	0.754	0.716
KK2	0.721	0.71	0.757	0.725
KK3	0.778	0.693	0.756	0.656
KK4	0.692	0.735	0.739	0.679
KN1	0.703	0.708	0.797	0.713
KN2	0.661	0.68	0.74	0.688
KN3	0.667	0.695	0.737	0.697
KN4	0.758	0.739	0.796	0.675
SE1	0.728	0.719	0.82	0.839
SE2	0.735	0.781	0.777	0.858
SE3	0.773	0.821	0.781	0.826
SE4	0.667	0.665	0.706	0.807
SE5	0.676	0.686	0.726	0.817

Table 4: Cross Loading

	Employee Engagement (Y)	Organization Climate(X2)	Organization Commitment (Z)	Self Efficacy (X1)
Employee Engagement (Y)	0.754			
Organization Climate (X2)	0.897	0.764		
Organization Commitment (Z)	0.93	0.911	0.759	
Self-Efficacy (X1)	0.865	0.888	0.92	0.83

Table 5: Discriminant Validity

Based on the data results that can be seen in the table above, it can be seen that each indicator in the research variable has a good cross loading and discriminant validity value in compiling their respective variables.

Construct Reliability and Validity	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
Self Efficacy	0.688	Valid
Organization Climate	0.584	Valid
Employee Engagement	0.568	Valid
Organization Commitment	0.576	Valid

Table 6: Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Based on the data results that can be seen in the table above, it can be seen that each indicator in the research variable has a good cross loading and discriminant validity value in compiling their respective variables.

Construct Reliability and Validity	CR	CA	Information
Self Efficacy	0.917	0.887	Reliable
Organization Climate	0.933	0.92	Reliable
Employee Engagement	0.957	0.952	Reliable
Organization Commitment	0.950	0.943	Reliable

Table 7: Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha

The resulting value, it can be said that all construction have good reliability in accordance with the required drinking value limit, which is above the value of 0.70.

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Engagement (Y)	0.88	0.876
Organization Commitment (Z)	0.889	0.886

Table 8: R-Square

Looking at the R-square (R2) output in the table above, it can be concluded that the structural model (inner model) in this study is classified as "good".

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model	Model Fit
SRMR	0.066	0.066	SRMR<0.08
d_ ULS	4.695	4.695	d_ ULS>2.000
d_ G	5.703	5.703	d_ G>0.900

Table 9: Goodness of Fit

From the table above, it can be that the SRMR value has met the criteria for the value of the category must be below 0.080 then the value on the d_ ULS must be above 2,000 indicating the fit model with the data for the GFI

value must be above 0.900 indicating a descriptive measure of model suitability the data is acceptable and fit it can be concluded that the alignment model or the inter-construction relationship criteria can be tested.

Hipotesis	Pengaruh	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
H1	Organization Climate (X2) -> Employee Engagement (Y)	2.723	0.007	Significance
H2	Organization Climate (X2) Organization Commitment (Z)	3.778	0	Significance
H3	Organization Commitment (Z) -> Employee Engagement (Y)	7.241	0	Significance
H4	Self Efficacy (X1) -> Employee Engagement (Y)	0.354	0.724	Not significance
H5	Self Efficacy (X1) -> Organization Commitment (Z)	4.507	0	Significance

Table 10: Direct Effect

From the results above, it is stated that because the RSA variable at the reliability test stage obtained reliable results so that the first hypothesis was accepted. This proves that the Organizational Climate has proven to have a positive influence on Employee Engagement.

The test results showed the value of the Organizational Climate beta coefficient to Organizational Commitment of 0 and the t-statistic of 3,778. From these results are expressed significant t-statistics. Because >1.96 with a p-value of <0.05 so the second hypothesis is accepted. This proves that the Organizational Climate is proven to have a positive influence on organizational commitments.

The test results showed that the beta coefficient value of Organizational Commitment to Employee Engagement was 0 and the t-statistic was 7.241. From these results are expressed significant t-statistics. Because <1.96 with a p-value of <0.05 so the third hypothesis is accepted. This

proves that Organizational Commitment is proven to have a positive influence on Employee Engagement.

The fourth hypothesis tests whether Self Efficacy positively affects Employee Engagement. The test results showed that the value of the beta coefficient of Self Efficacy to Employee Engagement was 0.724 and the statistical value was 0.354. From this result, the t-statistics were not significant, because <1.96 with a p-value of >0.05 so that the fourth hypothesis was not accepted. This proves that Self Efficacy is proven to have no positive influence on Employee Engagement.

The test results showed that the value of the beta coefficient of Self Efficacy to Organizational Commitment was 0 and the statistical was 4.507. From this result, significant t-statistics were obtained, because >1.96 with a p-value of <0.05 so that the fifth hypothesis was accepted. This proves that Self Efficacy is proven to have a positive influence on Organizational Commitment.

		T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Value s	Information
Organization Commitment Mediates the relationship between Self Efficacy and Employee Engagement (H6)	Self Efficacy (X1) Organization Commitment (Z) -> Employee Engagement (Y)	3.344	0.001	Significance
Organizational Commitment Mediates the relationship between Organization Climate and Employee Engagement (H7)	Organization Climate (X1) -> Organization Commitment (Z) -> Employee Engagement (Y)	3.918	0.000	Significance

Table 11: Indirect Effect

The results from the table above, show that indirectly, H6 Organizational Climate affects Employee Engagement through Organizational Commitments of 0.307. This also means that Employee Engagement will increase along with the increasing Organizational Climate in a company. If not through Organizational Commitment, then the Organizational Climate does not affect employee engagement much.

For H7 Self Efficacy, it affects Employee Engagement through Organizational Commitment of 0.360. This also means that Employee Engagement will increase along with the increase in employee Self-Efficacy in a company. If not through Organizational Commitment, then the Organizational Climate does not affect employee engagement much.

There is a positive and significant influence of the organizational climate on employee engagement, so the first hypothesis is tested and acceptable. This can be interpreted to mean that the more employees feel that the conditions of their work environment are comfortable, the greater the employee's work attachment to his company [7].

This is also reinforced by previous research on organizational climate and employee work attachment found that the more positive the organizational climate felt by employees, the higher the employee's work attachment will be. In addition, the organizational climate and psychological capital of each are factors that have a significant influence on work attachment [8].

There is a positive and significant influence of the organizational climate on organizational commitment, so the second hypothesis is tested and acceptable. This can be interpreted to mean that the more employees feel comfortable in their work environment, the greater the employee's commitment to their company. These results are in line with previous research that found that the organizational climate affects employee commitment [9]. Other researchers state that the organizational climate has a significant positive effect on organizational commitment [10].

There is a positive and significant influence of organizational commitment to employee engagement, so the third hypothesis is tested and acceptable. This can be interpreted to mean that the higher the employee's organizational commitment, the greater the employee's work attachment to his company. In addition, loyalty, a sense of responsibility, which is well perceived by employees, turns out to have a positive impact on the employee's work attachment to his company.

There is no positive and significant influence of self-efficacy on employee engagement, so the fourth hypothesis is rejected. It can be concluded that the higher the self-efficacy of employees in a company, it is not enough to make the employee's work attachment better. This result is an interesting finding, because the results of previous studies found that self-efficacy has a significant influence on employee engagement [10].

There is a positive and significant influence of self-efficacy on organizational commitment, so the fifth hypothesis is tested and acceptable. This can be interpreted to mean that the higher the employee's self-efficacy, the greater the employee's organizational commitment to his company.

These results were corroborated by his bilium research which found that self-efficacy has a positive and significant influence on organizational commitment in a company [11]. In addition, self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment [12].

The organizational climate (work environment in the company) that is felt by employees is getting better, it will have a positive influence on employee work attachment [13][14]. Self-efficacy or self-efficacy owned by employees is high, it will have a positive impact on organizational commitment, where the results will affect the employee's work attachment to his company [15].

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results of this research related to the influence of employee Self-efficacy (SE) on employee engagement (EE) in general do not have a close relationship, the lowest indicator in the self-efficacy dimension is the SE 4 indicator, where technical knowledge and training or work procedures have not been optimally owned by employees. This makes the ability to complete the work entrusted to employees low. As for the most dominant indicator in self-efficacy is that employees in their work already feel that

they are compatible with their abilities, so with this sense of compatibility, it is closely related to employee engagement in a company.

For conclusions regarding the influence of Organization Climate (IO) on Employee Engagement (EE), that the indicators of responsibility, duties and authorities, communication between employees, support and assistance as well as conflicts between employees in this study show that it is good where this is closely related to the spirit, dedication and perseverance of employees towards work and the company. Another thing, the most influential indicator is employee responsibility, where employees feel that the company has high work standards and they understand the duties and responsibilities in their work to be the most dominant factor related to employee engagement in a company. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator is communication between colleagues, which is closely related to the effect on employee engagement.

The conclusion regarding the effect of Organization Commitment (KO) on employee engagement (EE), indicates that the influence of organizational commitment on employee engagement in this study is the most dominant factor. Meanwhile, the highest indicator of the organizational commitment dimension is that employees feel they are working not only for profit, and they also feel loyal to the company so they feel it is difficult to leave the company. Meanwhile, the lowest indicator in organizational commitment is that employees feel that the company has not meant much to them to be the least influence related to employee engagement.

The influence of Self Efficacy (SE) on Organization Commitment (KO), shows that in general it is very good. The lowest indicator is the technical knowledge of employees in completing their work, which is related to the employee's organizational commitment. Meanwhile, the factor of employees who feel that their work is suitable will be closely related to their commitment to the company.

The influence of Organization Climate (IO) on Organization Commitment (KO), sourced from the submission of hypotheses and the results of research analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that a good Organizational Climate within a company is closely related to organizational commitments in the company. The most influential indicator is employee responsibility, where employees feel that the company has high work standards and they understand the duties and targets of achieving the company so that this is the most dominant factor that is closely related to employee engagement in a company. Meanwhile, the lowest factor in the organizational climate is communication between employees which is still not good, which will affect in general the organizational commitment of employees in a company.

Further research in order to be able to use and consider the results of this study, which is by looking at the results of dimensions that are already significant and insignificant between the constructs used. Finally, researchers can then

also use other instruments such as interviews with respondents, in order to get more complete research results.

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